

End-users' social acceptance survey

FER-PLAY

Dear participant,

Thank you for your interest! This survey is part of the FER-PLAY project. The goal is to understand your perception on circular fertilisers.

Answering the survey should take you 5 min.

Thank you very much for your time!

Kind regards,

FER-PLAY team

Prior to start, we would like to give you concept definitions that will be later used in this survey.

Definitions

For the needs of this questionnaire we are using the following definitions:

Synthetic fertiliser: human-made substances used to enrich soil nutrient content for plant growth, composed of chemical compounds that provide essential nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. Examples: ammonium nitrate, superphosphate, potassium chloride, etc.

Circular fertiliser: organic or recycled products coming from secondary raw materials that are used to improve soil health and promote plant growth in a sustainable manner by minimizing waste and utilizing renewable resources. Examples: compost, biochar, struvite, etc.

The collected answers, besides analysed and managed data will be performed according to the European General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679/EU) and ethical requirements. Answers will be totally anonymous and no results can be connected to individual persons. All of this will be overseen by the FER-PLAY Open Science and Data Manager. By participating, you accept these conditions.

Farmer's characteristics

1. In which country do you reside?	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
2. What is your age range?	<input type="checkbox"/> 18-24 <input type="checkbox"/> 25-38 <input type="checkbox"/> 35-44 <input type="checkbox"/> 45-54 <input type="checkbox"/> 55-64 <input type="checkbox"/> 65 or older
3. What is your gender?	<input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Not binary <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say
4. Are you a farmer or a technician?	<input type="checkbox"/> Farmer <input type="checkbox"/> Technician
5. What type of farming is being carried out in your field?	<input type="checkbox"/> Conventional <input type="checkbox"/> Organic / Biodynamic / Symbiotic <input type="checkbox"/> In transition <input type="checkbox"/> Others (regenerative, low inputs, etc.)
6. What are you farming activities?	<input type="checkbox"/> Arable <input type="checkbox"/> Mixed <input type="checkbox"/> Livestock <input type="checkbox"/> Others <input type="checkbox"/> Fruit <input type="checkbox"/> Vine <input type="checkbox"/> Vegetables

7. What is your farm size in hectares?	<input type="checkbox"/> Lower than 20 ha <input type="checkbox"/> 20 to 400 ha <input type="checkbox"/> More than 400 ha
8. What type of fertiliser are you currently using?	<input type="checkbox"/> Synthetic <input type="checkbox"/> Compost <input type="checkbox"/> Manure <input type="checkbox"/> Stabilized material (sludge, digestate)

Farmer's preferences

9. Please score the following factors according to the relevance when selecting a fertiliser to you:

	Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Form (e.g. solid, liquid)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ease of use / application	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Currently used machinery	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Nutrient content and composition	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Cost	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Environmental aspects	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Production sustainability	<input type="checkbox"/>				

10. Select which type of fertilizer you think the different characteristics belong to:

	Synthetic	Circular	Do not know
Lower nutrient content supplied	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Higher environmental pollution including its production and transport	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
More affected by external conditions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Easily applied and mixed in soils	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Better nutrient control for application	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Improvement of soil quality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It has some limitations depending on the soil and crop	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It can require training for a correct application	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

11. At what level are you aware of the current legislation regarding fertiliser?

- EU National Regional

12. Do you typically review updated to legislation (at any level) at least once a year?

- Yes No

13. Please score the information sources from the lowest (1) to the highest (5) trust you have:

	Not trustworthy	Slightly trustworthy	Moderately trustworthy	Very trustworthy	Extremely trustworthy
Fertiliser producers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Technical advisor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialised press	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Neighbouring farmer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salesperson	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Environmental NGOs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Farmers association	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Public authorities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. How concerned are you about the environmental impact of the fertiliser?

From 1 (Not concerned) to 5 (Extremely concerned)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

15. How concerned are you about the cost of the fertiliser?

From 1 (Not concerned) to 5 (Extremely concerned)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

16. How concerned are you about the performance of the fertiliser?

From 1 (Not concerned) to 5 (Extremely concerned)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

17. How important is it for you that the fertiliser is sustainable and environmentally friendly?

From 1 (Not important) to 5 (Extremely important)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

18. How much do you believe that a circular fertiliser will improve soil health?

From 1 (Not likely) to 5 (Extremely likely)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

19. How important is it for you that a circular fertiliser is locally produced?

From 1 (Not important) to 5 (Extremely important)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

20. How easy is it to find circular fertilisers locally?

From 1 (Not easy) to 5 (Extremely easy)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

21. How likely are you to switch from your current fertiliser to a circular one (e.g., from triple superphosphate to struvite)?

From 1 (Not likely) to 5 (Extremely likely) - If you already use a circular fertiliser, you do not need to answer this question.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

22. Under what circumstances would you be willing to use circular fertilisers?

You can select more than one answer.

- Subsidied or free of charge
- Cheaper than conventional fertilisers
- Same price as conventional fertilisers
- Slightly more expensive than conventional fertilisers
- Not willing to substitute
- I already use a circular fertiliser

23. Please specify which circular fertiliser you currently use (if you use one) :

24. Are you interested in trying other circular fertilisers? Please specify

25. Knowing that the production of circular fertilisers comes from secondary raw materials (residues), what do you think about the following statements?

	Very disagree	Slightly disagree	Moderately agree	Slightly agree	Very agree
The inconvenience that their production could cause is offset by the benefits of circularity that they provide					
This type of industry provides circular advantages and I support them					

26. Would you mind if this industry is located less than 2 km from your home?

- Yes. I do not want this industry near my home
- No. I do not care

27. If you answered yes, what minimum distance do you consider acceptable for it to be settled in?

2-5 km	5-10 km	10-15 km	15-20 km	More than 20 kms
--------	---------	----------	----------	------------------

28. Are there any limitations on the availability or accessibility of the circular fertilisers in your area?

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

29. Please specify the limitations you are facing :

fer ▶ play

A stylized wheat stalk logo with a green stem and a brown base, positioned between the 'p' and 'ay' of the 'fer ▶ play' text.

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101060426.”

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

